

TEACHER BURNOUT IN THE CLASSROOM: AN INQUIRY INTO CAUSES AND COPING STRATEGIES

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Abstract. This study explored the experiences of teachers' burnout in the classroom. Specifically, it aimed to answer their perceptions about it simultaneously as the coping mechanisms for the emerging challenges. To achieve the objectives of the study, I made use of phenomenology. The 10 participants of this study were female teachers of Panibasan Elementary School, Maco North District, Davao de Oro Division. I used a semi-structured online interview using the coding technique to analyze the data. The study disclosed different themes, such as in the first Objective, experiences of teachers' burnout in the workplace. The results were excessive workload, student challenges, underpaid, and lack of incentives. The second objective is to provide Coping strategies for teachers to the challenges they perceive as effective in preventing workplace burnout. In collecting results, themes are self-care and time management. In summary, these emergent themes provide insights that emphasize the significance of holistic approaches to teacher well-being. Educational institutions and legislators may support a more resilient and contented teaching workforce by cultivating a culture that prioritizes work-life balance, supports self-care, and offers tools for efficient time management. It was essential to identify and address these coping mechanisms to foster an atmosphere in which educators can flourish on the job while preserving their general well-being. In order to avoid becoming overburdened, educators understand the importance of setting limits, prioritizing work, and effectively managing their workload. Teachers may benefit from professional development options that emphasize time management techniques. Providing tools and resources to educators that facilitate task streamlining, good planning, and goal-setting leads to a more sustainable workload.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher burnout
2. Coping Strategies
3. Coping Styles

1. Introduction

Teacher burnout in the classroom is a pressing issue that significantly impacts the quality of education and the well-being of educators. The causes of burnout are multifaceted, often stemming from excessive workload, lack of support, high-stakes testing, and the emotional toll of managing diverse student needs. Teachers facing burnout may experience chronic stress, fatigue, and a diminished sense of personal accomplishment, leading to decreased job satisfaction and performance. To address this, effective coping strategies are essential. These include fostering a supportive work environment, providing professional development opportunities focused on stress management, encouraging collaboration among staff, and promoting a healthy

work-life balance. Teachers have a crucial influence. Teachers have an essential role in the growth and development of students outside the home. Other vocations rely on instructors to flourish and progress. However, as a result of the rising demands and higher expectations of what instructors must achieve in the classroom, job stress and how teachers deal with it have become a more significant issue (McCarthy, Lambert, O'Donnell, Melendres, 2009). According to Abel and Sewell (2019), teacher stress is not just rooted in overcrowded classrooms or rough, urban communities; teacher stress can also be identified in rural classroom settings with a smaller population of children. Scholarly research on teacher stress and coping identifies that teacher stress leads to burnout, emotional strain, and, in some cases, leaving the profession altogether. Chang (2009) discusses this theory and draws attention to the high levels of stress that affect teachers' internal and external abilities if coping strategies are not implemented. The American Psychological Association (2011) reported that most Americans identify their stress levels as being five or higher on a scale of 1 to 10. In comparison, over half of the teachers experience some form of stress; however, only 7

However, during the last twenty years, the number of seasoned teachers remaining in the profession has declined (Rinke Mawhinney, 2019). According to the 2019-2020 statistics from the Massachusetts Department of Elementary and Secondary Education (MADESE), there was a total of 76,572 teachers working throughout the state (MADESE, 2020). By the end of the school year, 69,560 teachers were retained (MADESE, 2020). This signifies that 1.1

Some of the reasons teacher burnout occurs include, but not exclusively, job demands, decreased compensatory measures, and a lack of being recognized by school administration for their efforts (Rinke Mawhinney, 2019). Burnout is a concept that was first researched by Freudenberger (2014). He classified the term

as related to a caring professional or an overly committed person who experiences workplace burnout (Heinemann Heinemann, 2017). Caring professionals can be described as persons in the human services profession, such as social workers, counselors, medical professionals, and teachers (Hargreaves Goodson, 1996). Freudenberger (2014) defines burnout as "becoming exhausted by excessive demands on energy, strength, or resources in the workplace." The teaching profession requires enthusiasm about the job and a willingness to care for the students in the classroom (Hargreaves, 2018). Therefore, teachers' burnout could negatively affect their job performance. Teachers are usually passionate about the lessons they create and their work for the students (Hargreaves, 2018). Emotions are at the heart of teaching. Emotions are a dynamic part of ourselves, and whether they are positive or negative, all organizations, including schools, are full of them" (Hargreaves, 1998). Since teaching is a balance of relationship building and educational practice, "teaching . . . involves and depends upon degrees of emotional understanding" (Hargreaves, 2018). Thus, having highly emotive and caring professionals who experience continuous stress could, in turn, lead to burnout (Heinemann Heinemann, 2017). Szigeti, Balázs, Bikfalvi, and Urbán (2017) likewise defined burnout as a "psychological response to chronic, work-related stress" (p. 530), which has many adverse symptomatic effects on a person, such as fatigue, sleep issues, trouble concentrating, depression and anxiety, appetite, and weight issues. The adverse effects for teachers might include but are not limited to frequent absenteeism, decline in positive peer and student relationships, and less tolerance for behavioral disruptions or incidents in the classroom (Lynch, 2016). According to Yildirim (2017), burnout is prevalent among teachers because they might not utilize the appropriate coping styles to manage their stress and conduct their teaching in the classroom. To avoid experienc-

ing burnout in the workplace, it would be beneficial for people to improve their emotional understanding (Hargreaves, 1998). Skaalvik (2010) indicated in their research that teaching is one of the most stressful professions. In the literature, teaching-related stress is described as negative feelings two such as depression, frustration, and tension. It also shows that professional burnout results in performing tasks less effectively and taking longer to complete them. Mearn and Cain (2003) recognized that among teachers, burnout has been linked to adverse outcomes and professional consequences, including emotional exhaustion, depression, impaired occupational functioning, and dissatisfaction with one's career choice. Burnout also negatively affects students and teachers' families (Westman, 2001). Particularly vulnerable are novice teachers, who may choose to leave the field due to burnout. Past estimates are that as many as 20It was essential to understand how teachers deal with the everyday demands and challenges associated with the teaching profession to alleviate stress, reduce the possibility of burnout, and promote classroom engagement and learning. Such information would help identify the coping process that targets early intervention and effective good practices. Shaalvick and Shaalvick (2016) indicated that stress in teaching can lead to decreased teacher motivation and engagement. According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary, stress is defined as bodily or mental tension resulting from factors that tend to alter an existent equilibrium. Day (2005) states that stress is not a helpful term because the term implies a phenomenon. Because of this disagreement among academics, stress is not well defined and, therefore, difficult to measure. Day (2005), who referenced Seyle's theory, suggests stress is "the non-specific response of the body to any demand for change" (p. 1199). The definition the author referenced will be used in this study. Three stress is challenging and, at times, complicated because teachers lack coping methods. According to Skinner and Beers (2016), some individual actions that respond to stressors, such as venting, problem-solving, and supporting, are also coping methods. A healthy work environment is where teachers recognize their stress and find ways to cope. In the Philippine context, Teaching is a challenging career with substantial stressors that can lead to professional burnout. As a primarily isolated profession—being the lone adult in the room for many hours each day—many teachers feel burdened by the many responsibilities and stressors they encounter. New teachers who have not yet developed coping mechanisms to help themselves feel less stressed and exhausted are particularly at risk of experiencing burnout. While some schools and districts have implemented professional development instruction for stress reduction, these solutions often only target daily stress and do not address the more long-term severe burnout. Burnout is a physical, emotional, and mental syndrome, including negative attitudes toward life, others, or a career (Akbaba, 2014). Burnout almost always includes feelings of exhaustion, long-term fatigue, despair or hopelessness, negative self-concept, and lack of productivity at work (Freudenberger Richelson, 1980). Research suggests that new teachers feel the effects of burnout more strongly than do teachers with many years of experience (Reichl et al, 2014). This can be seen in high turnover rates, with as many as one-third of new teachers leaving the profession within their first three years (Carroll Foster, 2008). Davao de Oro was a very progressive city since, to them, mental and physical well-being depended on how well individuals handled the psychosocial, contextual, and physical challenges and demands of their environments. Although stress is a necessary and sometimes proper physiologic response, continuous exposure to high levels of occupational stress may lead to burnout. Burnout is a psychosocial phenomenon characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonaliza-

tion, and diminished personal fulfillment. Over the past two decades, teacher burnout has been recognized as a severe professional problem, affecting teachers' motivation and job satisfaction, with consequences for students' learning and behavior and the broader school environment. Compared with other careers, teaching has been identified as one with the highest levels of perceived stress. According to, school

as a professional environment is characterized by several contexts susceptible to emotional exhaustion that vary from school to school and within the same school. The concept of "professional environment demands" refers to physical, social, or organizational attributes of a professional context that require prolonged physical and mental effort.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This research study aims to identify teachers' perceptions of coping with workplace burnout. Studying the available resources for teachers to cope with workplace burnout effectively would also be an opportunity. This could help schools be places where staff and students enjoy learning and being in the school daily. This researcher chose to conduct this study of workplace burnout to determine if teachers are using effective coping styles. It is also an opportunity to raise awareness of programs and resources available to staff members. This study also aims to identify their coping mechanisms to address the challenges. This is to understand the different challenges teachers experience in dealing with burnout in the school.

1.2. Research Questions—The study aims to investigate teachers perceived as both teachers and mothers. It also looks into their first-hand experiences as mothers and teachers to their children. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of teachers' burnout in the workplace?
- (2) How do they cope with the challenges as they perceive effective preventing workplace burnout?
- (3) What educational management insights were drawn from the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Definitions are provided for key terms used throughout this study that the reader may not recognize (Bloomberg Volpe, 2016). Key terms may have varied meanings, so providing definitions assisted the reader in understanding how the words are used in the context of this study (Bloomberg Volpe, 2016). Burnout: Exhaustion of physical or emotional strength or motivation, usually due to prolonged stress or frustration on the job (Maslach Leiter, 2016). Coping Skills: The use of coping strategies to reduce unfavorable emotions. (American Psychological

Association, 2020). Coping Strategies: Methods in which people learn to accept, reduce, or eliminate—stressful encounters (Auduly, 2016). Coping Styles: Using cognitive and behavioral strategies to reduce the negative feelings caused by stress (American Psychological Association, 2020). Depersonalization: Removal from socially interacting with others. A sense of being guarded (Maslach Leiter, 2016). Encourage: To inspire with courage, spirit, or hope (Bandura, 1986). Fatigue: A state of exhaustion. It is a feeling exhibited by stress or not enough sleep. (American Psychological Association, 2020).

1.4. Significant of the Study—Teachers are given insight into the experiences and challenges that other teachers have when it comes

to dealing with burnout in the workplace. This would help them prepare as they would know how to solve problems that may occur while uti-

lizing the approach. Policy/program implementors could use the results of this study to create policies and programs for teachers to help the teachers better implement teaching and learn-

ing. Lastly, this research would help other researchers if they wish to conduct a similar or comparative study.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research is highly anchored on Maslach’s (1982) theory of burnout and Bandura’s (1986) social cognitive theory are the foundational frameworks for this study. According to Maslach, burnout has been recognized as an occupational hazard for many years for various people-oriented professions, such as human services, education, and health care. There are similarities between the theories where the feelings of burnout are driven by internal and external factors and by how teachers manage their emotions (Alessandri et al., 2018). Social cognitive theory “adopts an agentic perspective to self-development, adaptation, and change” (Bandura, 2005). The focus of Bandura’s theory is on how people can learn by observing and modeling based on environmental or social factors causing life changes, positive or negative (Bandura, 2005). A person can learn new strategies to manage different situations through effective modeling. Maslach’s burnout theory is human-centered (Maslach Leiter, 2016). This means that the focus of the behavior is on the whole person and how the individual reacts to events or situations. Initially, her theory on burnout Maslach (1982) focused on health care professionals and how caring for patients led to exhaustion, self-efficacy, and cynicism. The theory expanded into other caring professions, such as teaching, to examine the burnout rate of educators (Maslach, 1982). Maslach’s (1982) burnout theory has been classified as the theory where the “worker feels as though they are no longer able to give of themselves at a psychological level, also known as emotional exhaustion” (p. 2). Maslach’s burnout theory relates to those in professions of working with other people, also known as

careers in human services. Working with others—in this case, teachers working with students—can be emotionally draining (Maslach Leiter, 2016). Maslach Burnout Theory Bandura Social Cognitive Theory MBI-Educator Survey Maslach’s (1982) burnout theory was first studied by conducting interviews with human service workers (teachers, counselors, social workers, etc.), resulting in an inventory of job satisfaction questionnaire (Maslach, 1982). The inventory included questions relative to Maslach’s burnout theory, which focused on emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishments. The significance of this three-dimensional model is that it clearly places the individual stress experience within a social context” (Cooper, 2018). Understanding the phenomenon of teacher burnout is important to this research in order to help signify the exhaustion and depersonalization teachers could be facing within their careers (Maslach, 2016). Weaknesses of burnout theory. Critics of Maslach’s burnout theory have suggested there are more than three factors, emotional exhaustion, lack of personal accomplishment, and depersonalization to burnout than Maslach outlines in the theory, (Densten, 2001). The additional factors include psychological and somatic strain relative to emotional exhaustion (Densten, 2001). Researchers have also posed that chronic burnout is not only related to work issues as the feelings continually happen outside of work (Bianchi, Trucot, Laurent, Brisson, Schofield, 2014). According to Bianchi et al. (2014), burnout should be seen as a “multi contextual syndrome” whereby the longevity of the stress-induced feelings can occur at any point for a person. Strengths of burnout theory.

Those critics who favored Maslach's burnout theory utilize the theory in the workplace because burnout is a phenomenon that no one had previously talked about (Maslach, 1993). Maslach's burnout theory examined the stress encountered on the job as a method for employers to evaluate workplace stressors (Taris, 31 LeBlanc, Schaufeli, Schreurs, 2005). Taris et al., (2005) also discussed how Maslach's theory was systemic in that the three factors can occur when an employee is encountering workplace burnout. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory Bandura (1986) developed a social cognitive theory, that explains how environmental and mental influences form a reaction to events (McLeod, 2016). Social cognitive theory is relative to a triadic process where the person, the behavior, and the environment influence one another (Schunk DiBenedetto, 2020). Examples of how social cognitive theory can be demonstrated include a person learning to play a sport or going on a new diet (Cherry, 2020). Social cognitive theorists are concerned with how the environment drives a person's motivation (Bandura, 1986). Schunk and DiBenedetto (2020) described social cognitive theory from the perspective that "what people think can affect their actions and environments, actions can alter their thoughts and environments, and environments can influence individuals' thoughts and actions. Within social cognitive theory, self-efficacy is presented as a motivational factor that people can learn to achieve within their careers (Anderson Kirkpatrick, 2016). Self-efficacy can be defined as how a person envisions themselves handling the situation (Bandura, 1999). Self-efficacy "plays a major role in how people perceive situations and how people behave in response to situations" (Cherry, 2020). Teachers manage the classroom, which includes but is not limited to lesson planning, behavior management, and interacting with the students and personnel. Relative to teachers experiencing workplace burnout, this theory will be used to determine if teachers actually self-report they are effectively managing their emotions related to workplace stress. Weaknesses of social cognitive theory. Criticism of Bandura's social cognitive theory included that the focus was on the thought process rather than the biological or hormonal response to an individual's reaction to a situation (LaMorte, 2019). Another criticism is that the theory focuses on how environmental change can instantly affect the individual. (LaMorte, 2019). Strengths of social cognitive theory. Those that favored Bandura's social cognitive theory (1986) felt that the theory focused on human actions and the conditions surrounding learned observation behaviors (McLeod, 2016). Others that favored social cognitive theory described the theory as a process to alleviate chronic issues and improve the outcome to a behavior/illness (Tougas, Hayden, McGrath, Huguet, Rozario, 2015). A strength of social cognitive theory is the topic of self-efficacy (Schunk, 2019). "Efficacy may influence teachers' activities, efforts, and persistence" (Schunk, 2019, p. 224) which causes increased motivation in the classroom.

2. Methodology

This chapter introduced the methods used in conducting the study and gathering data. This also included the research design, philosophical assumptions, research participants and sampling, data collection, research instrument, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

contexts. In-depth interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics were being explored. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group’s cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asked the question, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of this phenomenon for these people?” The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the school heads in the new normal as they tried to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that was greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions*—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It established the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions had different types and were elaborated below. Good research involved undertaking the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. A decent study task began with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigma), meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm was the patterning of a person’s thinking; it was a principal example among examples, an exemplar or model

to follow according to which design actions were taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an act of submitting to a view (Stanage 2007). This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defined a research paradigm as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action,” dealing with first principles, “ultimates,” or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertained to how the issue related to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality was subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addressed the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities existed, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and

those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, realities on the implementation of the curriculum in the past and the present were discussed by the participants, and the researcher tried to look into their ways of coping with the implementation in the new normal. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. I upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I would identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual

researchers “hold explicit belief”. The intention of this study is to gather information from the participants as to how they implemented the program following the guidelines set by DepEd. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and the coping strategies of the teachers in implementing the program in the new normal. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant’s answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant’s personal interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the teachers’ experiences as they adopted the new mode of learning implementation amidst the pandemic.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the teachers’ experiences were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI), and their coping strategies were extracted from the participants. The researcher’s inquisitiveness

on the experiences of the School Heads became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013), considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena”. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers having dual roles in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the

themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that

the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the subjective experiences and perspectives of the participants would provide highlights as to how the program was implemented before COVID-19 and how it is currently executed.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological research design. The phenomenological design describes the participants' interpretations of their experiences. The participants were required to respond to the questions provided to them via Google Forms. After, they were requested to participate in a Focus Group Discussion virtually and face-to-face, depending on the situation. At the end of this study, themes and common patterns were extracted from their responses (Jamon Cabanes, 2019). They decided to use a qualitative phenomenological research design because they would dwell on the individual experiences of the teachers under the new normal in Philippine public education. There were 10 teachers as participants of the study who had firsthand experiences in the new normal in Philippine public education. The data gathered were recorded, transcribed, and validated to extract first-hand experiences on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the new normal in Philippine public education from the teachers' lived experiences. The Colaizzi method of data analysis was used in a phenomenological research design. This is purely academic. The partici-

pants signed the informed consent form, and there was no risk in this study. They could withdraw anytime as a participant in the study. Ethical considerations and safety health protocols were followed. Phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The approach's fundamental goal is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews are conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced in terms of the phenomenon? What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)? Other forms of data such as documents, observations, and art may also be used. The data is then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon.

2.4. Research Participants—

In the selection of the research participants, I used the purposive sampling design, as participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the investigation. This design is additionally known as judgemental, selective, or subjective sampling. The participants were carefully chosen to guarantee the findings were authentic (Marshall, 1996). It was a non-probability sampling method and it occurs when elements selected for the sample were chosen by the judgment of the researcher. Researchers

often believe they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples. Ten (10) female teachers with children were part of the in-depth interview, and they were female teachers in Panibasan Elementary School, Maco North District, Davao de Oro Division. Moreover, coding will be used to protect the participants' identity. IDI-FT1 to IDI-FT10 was used for the informants of the in-depth interview.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Creswell (2007) emphasized that qualitative researchers face many ethical issues that surface during data collection analysis and dissemination of qualitative reports. In this study, I would deal with teachers in public schools to ensure an authentic response from the participants; I was responsible for exercising extra caution and maintaining the confidentiality of the study. The rights of the participants will be highly considered. Besides, they would not be forced to be part of the study when they would refuse. In protecting the identity of the participants, Glesne and Peshkins (1992) suggested that providing and assigning numbers or aliases could protect the anonymity of the participants. In this study, I used codes to protect the identity of the participants. Added to this, as the researcher, I explained the purpose and significance of the study. The participants would be allowed to ask the researcher questions about the nature of the study. This certifies that the information is clear to the participants. Moreover, the data gathering and the participation of the participants are guided by the Informed Consent Form, which is signed by the chosen participants. Lastly, the results and findings were returned to the participants for verification. The transcriptions of the recorded interview were kept private. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their

information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This would provide the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information that they feel might identify them. The researcher will reserve the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully at the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher would ensure that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would

be completed at the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study would not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically, in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher would necessarily express great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher

respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher would also always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty is present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data and or results are included, or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—In this study, I played various roles to attain the study's success. First, I asked for permission to conduct the study, which started with the school division Superintendent and then with the participants of my study. As a researcher, if consented, I have recorded the actual interview to achieve the needs of this type of research. The interview aimed to better understand the learners' expe-

riences in the new normal way of teaching and learning. The interview would also include how the Department of Education should improve its programs. After gathering the needed data, I transcribed and analyzed everything. However, human instruments were more important to study in case the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions regarding the persons involved in the research (Greenbank, 2003).

2.7. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they would provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as interviews or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must

decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, I employed the following data-gathering steps. I asked the Schools Division Superintendent for permission to conduct the study in Panibasan Elementary School, Maco North District, Division of Davao De Oro. I secured the superintendent's permission. I sent the superintendent a letter explaining the study's objectives and the participants' identification, with an attached copy of Chapters 1 and 2 and the research instrument. I would only start after I received the Superintendent's approval. I asked the school heads for permission. After securing approval from the SDS, I sent letters to the principals of the identified schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. I obtained consent from the participants and considered the participants' consent as informants

of the study a priority; thus, I ensured permission from them and their parents/guardians. The participants were adequately oriented about the whole study process and their part as participants. I conducted the interview. I used the interview questionnaire to conduct an in-depth interview. I took participants' profiles, took notes, and recorded conversations using a sound recorder for easy transcription. Likewise, I carefully listened and actively responded during the interviews. I was transcribing the interviewees' responses. The researcher would then precisely transcribe them by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with a full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences to direct the focus to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individuals were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping,

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework for this study was flexible enough to allow the researcher to either gather all of the data and then analyze it or evaluate it while it was being collected. The data collected was then sifted, charted, and categorized in line with key topics and themes during the analysis stage. This process involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization was

participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. Categorizing and coding the data would come after the transcription process. Themes were extracted, and participants' data were contrasted and compared. The researcher would then conduct a second round of interviews (FGD) to confirm data requiring more justification and participant feedback. The newly acquired material was carefully analyzed and added to the existing body of knowledge. Then, in order to identify patterns and trends, data were contrasted and compared between the individuals.

statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, he wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study.

becoming familiar with the data through reading and re-reading interview transcripts. Familiarizing the whole interview with the audio recording and transcript and any contextual or reflective notes the researcher recorded was a vital stage in interpretation. It could also be helpful to re-listen to all or parts of the audio recording. The researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, exploring the field, or reading transcripts. The researcher would become aware of critical ideas and re-

curing themes throughout the procedure and would make a note of them. The researcher may be unable to review all of the material due to the enormous amount of data that might be collected in qualitative research. As a result, a portion of the data set would be utilized. Several elements of the data collection method would influence the selection. Coding was the process of summarizing and representing data to provide a systematic account of the recorded or observed phenomenon. After familiarization, the researcher carefully reads the transcript line by line, applying a paraphrase or label that is a 'code' that describes what they have interpreted in the passage as necessary. Coding aimed to classify all of the data so that it could be compared systematically with other parts of the data set. Developing a thematic framework happens after coding a few transcripts. The researcher needs to compare the labels applied and select a set of codes to apply to all subsequent tran-

scripts. Codes could be grouped into categories, which are then clearly defined. This forms a working analytical framework. Several iterations of the analytical framework were likely required before no additional codes emerged. It was always worth having another code under each category to avoid ignoring data that does not fit; the analytical framework was never 'final' until the last transcript had been coded. Indexing involves identifying portions or sections of data that relate to a specific theme. This procedure is conducted using all textual data collected, such as transcripts of interviews. Ritchie and Spencer (1994) suggest using a numerical system to index references and annotating them in the margin beside the text for ease. Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for this task. Charting involves summarizing the data by category from each transcript. Good charting requires an ability to strike a balance between reducing the data on

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness was very important because the results and findings of the research study depended on the process of how it was being conducted by the researcher. Trustworthiness of a research study was important to evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustworthiness made the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts,

2016). Credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the issue of credibility, interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Transferability was concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study could be applied to other situations. In positivist work, the concern often lies in demonstrating that the results of the work at hand could be applied to a wider population since the findings of a qualitative project are specific to a small number of particular environments and individuals. It is impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions apply to other situations and populations. Therefore, to ensure transferability, I acknowledged that it is my responsibility as a researcher to ensure sufficient contextual transformation about the fieldwork

Figure 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

sites to enable the reader to make such a transfer. Confirmability was associated with objectivity in science, which was the use of instruments that were not dependent on human skill and perception. It was, however, difficult to ensure real objectivity since, as even tests and questionnaires are designed by humans, the intrusion of the researcher's biases is inevitable. Here, steps must be taken to help ensure as far as possible that the work's findings were the result of the

experiences and ideas of the participants, rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher. Dependability involves participants evaluation of the findings, interpretation and recommendations of the study such that all were supported by the data as received from participants of the study. Confirmability The degree to which the findings of the research study could be confirmed by other researchers.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, I explored the intricate narratives, themes, and patterns that surfaced during qualitative data analysis. Our primary goal was to comprehensively account for participants' experiences and perspectives and the contextual factors influencing them. Systematically examining these components aims to address the research questions and contribute to a more profound comprehension of the investigated phenomenon. Before delving into the discussion, it was essential to establish the symbols used to present quotations derived from participants' responses in the study. Codes were employed to reference the research participants within the transcribed interviews. As we embark on the journey through the results and discussion, it is crucial to maintain reflexivity, acknowledging the researcher's influence in shaping interpretations. The insights gained from this chapter not only shed light on the intricacies of the phenomenon but also serve as inspiration for future inquiries into the dynamic world we have explored.

3.1. Teachers' perceptions of burnout in the workplace.—Research questions number 1

what is the lived experience of teachers in diverse classrooms?

3.1.1. Excessive Workload—Many teachers perceive excessive workload, including heavy teaching schedules, lesson planning, grading, and administrative tasks, as contributing significantly to burnout. Excessive workload is a common factor contributing to burnout among teachers. This issue encompasses a variety of tasks and responsibilities that, when overwhelming or unmanageable, can lead to stress, exhaustion, and a decline in overall well-being. Teachers often have demanding teaching schedules with numerous classes throughout the day. Preparing and delivering lessons and addressing students' needs can be time-consuming and

mentally draining. Creating engaging and effective lesson plans requires significant time and effort. Teachers must also design activities, assessments, and adapt materials to cater to their students' diverse learning styles. Grading assignments, tests, and other assessments is a time-intensive task. Managing the volume of grading, providing meaningful feedback, and keeping up with assessment demands can contribute to workload stress. Teachers are often responsible for administrative duties such as attendance tracking, reporting, and documentation. These tasks add to the overall workload and can take time away from instructional activities.

3.1.2. Student Challenges—Disruptive behaviors in the classroom can significantly [impact teachers in various ways, both personally and professionally. Dealing with disruptive behaviors can be emotionally and mentally draining for teachers. The constant need to manage disruptions and maintain control in the classroom can lead to increased stress levels and, over time, contribute to burnout. Disruptive behaviors can hinder the teaching and learning process. Teachers may find it challenging to deliver lessons effectively and engage students when disruptions occur frequently. This can affect the overall quality of education in the classroom. Teachers spend a significant amount of time and energy addressing disruptive behaviors, which detracts from their primary role of

facilitating learning. This can reduce the time for planning lessons, providing individualized attention to students, and professional development. Teachers may experience a range of negative emotions, including frustration, anger, and helplessness when dealing with disruptive behaviors. These emotions can affect their overall job satisfaction and well-being. Disruptive behaviors can create a hostile classroom atmosphere. This affects the teacher and influences the learning experience for other students. A disruptive environment can make it challenging for all students to focus and succeed academically. Frequent disruptions can strain the relationships between teachers and students. Teachers may find it challenging to establish a positive rapport with disruptive students, which can impact the overall classroom dynamic.

3.1.3. Underpaid and lack of incentives—Teachers may feel burnt out if they perceive a lack of recognition or appreciation for their efforts, both from the school administration and the broader community. Furthermore, historically speaking, teacher pay gaps have always been an issue. Lynch (2016) describes the pay inequalities teachers face as an issue that has always been around. He states that there was no scarce need for teachers in the mid-19th century, and when the first teacher shortage occurred in the 20th century, they tackled this issue by establishing education departments at the collegiate level to attract college students instead of implementing salary increases (Lynch, 2016). A study done in California focuses on teacher pay related to quality. Cebula et al (2015) conclude that although there are many factors pertaining to student success, the amount teachers are paid affects academic performances of students. While examining pay for performance and its effects, it has been concluded that districts that implement pay incentives have more appeal for old and new teachers alike. Teacher performance pay, also known as pay for perfor-

mance or PFP includes higher incentives and pay based on student success. Inequalities in teacher pay are a historical issue that connects to the most important concerns in education today- addressing the teacher shortage and increasing the quality and retention of good teachers. Teachers are severely underpaid while being expected to do more than most professionals. (Anderson 2019) Han (2021) explains that “the quality of teachers has been pointed out as the key to successful educational reform. If teachers are truly underpaid, and if the best teachers have attractive options outside teaching, improving teacher quality seems almost unachievable with the limited resources”. Instead of blaming the issue on lack of funding and deeming it unattainable, my research has concluded that if we want quality educators, we must supply livable wages (Han, 2021). Figure 4 shows the emerging themes in the teachers’ perceptions regarding burnout in the workplace. The first theme that emerged was excessive workload. In the life of a teacher, the term “workload” takes on a weighty significance, not just in the sheer volume of tasks but in its profound impact on

Figure 3. *Perceptions of the Teachers Regarding Burnout in the Workplace*

daily life, well-being, and the very essence of the teaching profession. From the early morning hours spent preparing lesson plans to the late-night grading sessions, the excessive workload is an ever-present companion, shaping the nar-

ative of a teacher’s professional journey. The second theme that emerged was student challenges; the teachers’ statements highlight the multifaceted nature of challenges that teachers

3.1.4. Self-Care—Another research question that the researcher seeks to answer is what coping strategies teachers use to address challenges they perceive as effective in preventing workplace burnout. Self-Care. It involves ensuring adequate sleep, a healthy diet, regular exercise, and engaging in activities that bring joy and relaxation outside of work. Self-care is crucial for teachers as it is pivotal in maintaining their overall well-being and effectiveness in the classroom. The participants T01, T02, and T03 said, Self-care significantly impacts the overall well-being of teachers in several ways. Firstly, it plays a crucial role in managing stress and preventing burnout, which are common challenges in the teaching profession. Reg-

ular self-care practices, such as mindfulness, exercise, and adequate rest, help reduce the physical and emotional toll of the job, contributing to improved mental health. Additionally, self-care positively influences interpersonal relationships. By taking time for personal needs and cultivating a healthy work-life balance, teachers can strengthen connections with colleagues, students, and their own families. Healthy relationships and a supportive social network contribute significantly to overall well-being. Ultimately, self-care for teachers is not just about relaxation; it’s a holistic approach that considers mental, emotional, and physical health. By attending to these aspects, teachers can maintain a higher level of overall well-being, fostering a positive and sustainable career in education.

3.1.5. Time Management—Effective time management was the theme that emerged based on the participants' responses it is a key strategy in preventing and easing teacher burnout. Teachers often have a multitude of responsibilities, from lesson planning to grading and administrative duties. Effective time management involves prioritizing tasks based on urgency and importance. By focusing on high-priority tasks first, teachers can ensure that essential responsibilities are addressed, reducing the likelihood of feeling overwhelmed. Effective time management involves recognizing when it's appropriate to delegate tasks or seek support from colleagues. Collaboration and shared responsibilities can alleviate individual workloads. Time management that includes scheduled breaks and opportunities for self-care is crucial for preventing burnout. Taking short breaks during the day,

scheduling time for relaxation or exercise, and ensuring adequate sleep are essential components of effective time management that contribute to overall well-being. Regularly reviewing and reflecting on time management strategies allows teachers to assess their effectiveness and make necessary adjustments. This adaptive approach helps educators refine their practices over time, minimizing stress and preventing burnout. The participants (T08, T09) cited that, Effective time management is a critical factor in alleviating teacher burnout, offering a structured approach to the demanding nature of the profession. By implementing well-defined time management strategies, teachers can organize their tasks, set priorities, and allocate dedicated time for various responsibilities. This intentional approach not only enhances productivity but also mitigates the overwhelming feeling of being constantly inundated with work.

3.1.6. Recognition Programs—Establish recognition programs that publicly acknowledge and celebrate teachers' hard work and achievements. This can boost morale and create a culture of appreciation within the school community. Recognition programs play a crucial role in fostering a positive and motivating work environment for teachers, significantly impacting their morale, job satisfaction, and overall performance. Such programs are designed to acknowledge and celebrate the efforts and achievements of educators, providing them with the recognition they deserve. Research indicates that when teachers feel valued and appreciated, their motivation and commitment to their work increase, leading to better educational outcomes for students (Shen et al., 2022). Effective recognition programs typically include a variety of components, such as awards, public acknowledgment, professional development opportunities, and monetary incentives, all of which contribute to creating a culture of appre-

ciation within schools (Duyar et al., 2023). For instance, peer nominations and student feedback can be integral parts of these programs, ensuring a fair and comprehensive selection process that genuinely reflects the teachers' impact (Goddard et al., 2021). Moreover, consistent and well-structured recognition programs can enhance collaboration and camaraderie among staff, as teachers who feel recognized are more likely to support and uplift their colleagues (Skaalvik Skaalvik, 2019). Thus, implementing and maintaining robust recognition programs is essential for schools aiming to boost teacher morale and foster a positive and productive educational environment. To summarize the emerging themes of the coping strategies of teachers and the challenges they perceived as effective in preventing workplace burnout. Teachers need to recognize the signs of burnout early on and take steps to address it. Seeking help and implementing coping strategies can contribute to long-term job satisfaction and well-being. The

Figure 4. Coping Strategies of Teachers to the Challenges as they Perceived as Effective in Preventing Workplace Burnout.

first emerging theme was self-care. Engaging in self-care practices, whether through mindfulness, regular exercise, or pursuing personal interests, equips teachers with the tools to manage

stress and prevent burnout. It fosters emotional resilience, allowing educators to navigate the inherent challenges of their profession with a positive mindset.

3.1.7. Promoting healthy life balance— Promoting a healthy life balance is essential for maintaining overall well-being and productivity, particularly in high-stress professions such as teaching. Achieving a healthy balance involves prioritizing self-care, setting clear boundaries between work and personal life, and engaging in activities that foster mental and physical health. For teachers, this might mean ensuring they allocate time for exercise, hobbies, and relaxation, which can help reduce stress and prevent

burnout. Schools and organizations play a crucial role in this by encouraging reasonable workloads, offering mental health resources, and fostering a supportive work environment. When individuals maintain a healthy life balance, they are more likely to experience improved job satisfaction, better performance, and enhanced relationships both at work and in their personal lives. This holistic approach to well-being not only benefits the individual but also contributes to a more positive and productive community overall.

3.1.8. Providing resources to teachers— Providing resources to teachers is crucial for fostering an effective and dynamic educational environment. Access to updated teaching materials, technology, and professional development

opportunities equips educators with the tools necessary to enhance their instructional methods and stay current with educational trends. Moreover, resources like mental health support and administrative assistance are vital for main-

Figure 5. Educational management Insights that can be Drawn from the Study as they perceived as effective in preventing workplace burnout the

taining teacher well-being, which in turn positively impacts student learning. Ensuring that teachers have the resources they need helps to mitigate burnout, increases job satisfaction, and promotes a culture of continuous improvement. This investment in teachers not only supports their professional growth but also leads to better student outcomes, creating a more robust and responsive educational system. Ultimately, when teachers are well-supported, they are better positioned to inspire and educate their students effectively. Based from the participants, equally important are professional development opportunities, which help teachers stay current with educational trends and best practices. Continuous professional development ensures that educators are equipped with the latest knowledge

and skills necessary to address diverse student needs and incorporate innovative teaching methods. This ongoing learning fosters a culture of excellence and adaptability within schools, allowing teachers to implement new strategies that enhance student engagement and achievement. Furthermore, professional development opportunities can reinvigorate teachers' passion for their profession, reducing burnout and promoting job satisfaction. By investing in their growth, schools not only improve the quality of education but also demonstrate a commitment to valuing and empowering their educators. This, in turn, can lead to a more motivated and effective teaching staff, ultimately benefiting the entire educational community.

Figure 5. The educational management insights gained from studying teachers dealing with burnout were discussed. Two themes emerged from this experience: promoting

healthy life balance and providing resources to teachers. Understanding the benefits of a healthy balanced life will motivate anyone to make necessary changes. Balance will improve

the lives of individual employees as well as the life balance will also increase employee productivity, health, and morale.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter of the study typically delves into the implications of the study's findings and outlines potential directions for future research. The introduction to this chapter serves as a bridge between the presented data and the broader significance of the research. It provides context for the implications discussed and highlights the potential impact and relevance of the study's outcomes. It delves into the profound implications derived from the rich qualitative data presented in the preceding chapters. In this section, we explore the practical significance of findings, drawing connections between the research outcomes and real-world applications. Additionally, lays the groundwork for future research endeavors by identifying avenues that warrant further exploration. As the researcher navigates the study's implications, the aimed to contribute valuable insights to the field, offering recommendations for practitioners, policymakers, and researchers. This chapter serves as a crucial link between the empirical evidence uncovered in qualitative research and the broader implications that extend beyond the immediate scope of the study.

4.1. Findings—The findings of the study revealed that perceptions of the teachers regarding burnout in the workplace, excessive Workload, Student Challenges, and Underpaid, and Lack of Incentives. The study's findings underscore the multifaceted nature of teacher burnout, with three primary causes emerging as significant contributors. Excessive workload emerged as a predominant factor, highlighting the strain on teachers dealing with an overwhelming array of responsibilities, from lesson planning to administrative tasks. Student challenges, including diverse learning needs and behavioral issues, were identified as another critical source of burnout, emphasizing the emotional toll educators face in addressing varied classroom dynamics. Additionally, the perception of being underpaid emerged as a significant stressor, reflecting the financial strain experienced by teachers. These findings collectively emphasize the urgent need for comprehensive interventions to address workload distribution, provide support for managing diverse student needs, and advocate for fair compensation, aiming to mitigate the pervasive issue of teacher burnout. On the other hand, the coping strategies of teachers to the challenges as they perceived as effective in preventing workplace burnout, Self-Care, Time Management, and Recognition Programs. The study's findings further highlighted self-care and time management as pivotal coping strategies for teachers grappling with burnout. Self-care emerged as a crucial aspect, emphasizing the importance of teachers prioritizing their mental, emotional, and physical well-being. Educators recognize the need for intentional efforts to alleviate stress and maintain a healthy work-life balance. Concurrently, time management surfaced as a primary coping mechanism, underlining the significance of strategic organization and prioritization of tasks to prevent overwhelming workloads. Teachers acknowledge the effectiveness of efficient time management in mitigating burnout by enabling them to navigate their responsibilities more effectively and establish clear boundaries. Together, these findings underscore the critical role of holistic approaches that encompass self-care and time management in fostering teacher resilience and well-being. Lastly, the educational management Insights that can be Drawn from the Study as they perceived as effective in preventing work-

place burnout, the study revealed an emerging themes was observed during the discussion. The emerged themes as follows: promoting healthy life balance and providing resources to teachers. Burnout can lead to physical, mental, and

emotional exhaustion, making it difficult for teachers to perform their duties effectively. Prioritizing self-care and work-life balance can help teachers prevent burnout and maintain their energy and enthusiasm for teaching

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The findings of the study revealed that perceptions of the teachers regarding burnout in the workplace, excessive Workload, Student Challenges, and Underpaid, and Lack of Incentives. They prioritize individual needs and interests, ensuring that each student's unique learning style and preferences are taken into account. Teachers promote collaboration and teamwork among students, encouraging them to work together and learn from one another. the coping strategies of teachers to the challenges as they perceived as effective in preventing workplace burnout, Self-Care, Time Management, and Recognition Programs. Secondly, recognizing student challenges as a major contributor to burnout underscores the need for tailored support mechanisms for teachers. The implementation of professional development programs

focusing on classroom management, differentiated instruction, and strategies for addressing diverse student needs can enhance teachers' capacity to navigate challenging situations. Lastly, the educational management Insights that can be Drawn from the Study as they perceived as effective in preventing workplace burnout, the study revealed an emerging themes was observed during the discussion. The emerged themes as follows: promoting healthy life balance and providing resources to teachers. the study's implications emphasize the importance of systemic changes in workload management, personalized support for teachers dealing with diverse student challenges, and efforts to address compensation issues. Furthermore, promoting self-care and time management as integral aspects of teacher well-being can contribute significantly to creating a sustainable and fulfilling environment within the education sector.

4.3. Future Directions—The research study was limited by its qualitative nature and by the research methodology itself. Due to the variables concerned, objectivity is often an important issue because the researcher interprets the data based on her understanding of the descriptions, perceptions, and insights provided by teachers who experience burnout in the workplace. The research findings would likely contribute to the research literature and inform and inspire all other teachers in public and private schools. The future directions of this study open avenues for continued exploration and improvement within the realm of teacher well-being and burnout. Firstly, there

was a need for longitudinal research to track the effectiveness of interventions stemming from the identified implications. Long-term studies could provide insights into the sustained impact of systemic changes in workload management, tailored support mechanisms, and compensation adjustments. Additionally, future research may delve into the nuanced aspects of student challenges, exploring specific interventions that prove most effective in addressing diverse learning needs and behavioral issues. This could involve the development and implementation of targeted professional development programs and support structures. Furthermore, investigations into the effectiveness of different self-care

and time-management interventions were warranted. Understanding which specific strategies and programs yield the most significant benefits for teachers could inform the design of more tailored and impactful well-being initiatives. Exploring the interplay between these factors and considering the unique contexts of various educational settings is crucial. Future studies might focus on how the identified implications interact in different school environments, considering regional, cultural, and institutional variations. Lastly, research may delve into the perspectives of policymakers, administrators, and other stakeholders to gauge their receptiveness to the identified implications and their willingness to implement changes. Understanding the systemic barriers to change and identifying strategies to overcome them would contribute to the successful implementation of future interventions.

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